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The International Politics of Peacekeeping

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Abstract:

The manifestation of international politics in peacekeeping is evident in the behavior of the big powers who are also occupying a permanent seat in the UN Security Council. The Security Council defines the mandate of operations and deploys the peacekeeping force to any area where there is conflict albeit with the consent of the host state. The force is obliged to be impartial and use minimal force. However, this article has argued that beyond the goal of ensuring ceasefire or conflict de-escalation, the UN peacekeeping force is an instrument in the hands of the big powers who through mandate definition project their interests.

Keywords: *International Politics; Peacekeeping; UN Security Council; Big Powers.*

INTRODUCTION:

According to (Richard Caplan in Encyclopedia Princetoniensis), Peacekeeping refers to the deployment of national or, more commonly, multinational forces for the purpose of helping to control and resolve an actual or potential armed conflict between or within states.¹ It was established by the United Nations (U.N.) in 1948² to maintain a ceasefire between two warring states or to prevent a conflict from jeopardizing global peace. Importantly, the UN peacekeeping force cannot intervene in any conflict without the consent of the host state. The consent of the host state is one of the three key principles of UN peacekeeping.³

The first UN peacekeepers (United Nations Truce Supervision Organization -UNTSO), were deployed to the Middle East and their missions were to observe and maintain a cease-fire between Israel and the Arab states during the 1948 Arab-Israeli war.⁴ Subsequently, the UN peacekeepers have participated in more than 70 missions around the globe.⁵ As of June 2024, the UN peacekeeping ongoing missions are 14.⁶

Even With a stationary *raison d'être*, peacekeeping operation has no permanent mandate. It is subject to the whims of international politics. It is merely an ad hoc response to problems and that is why it is difficult to categorize based on the tasks fulfilled by peacekeepers in different periods of history.⁷

In light of the above, this paper seeks to discuss peacekeeping in the context of international politics. To put it simply, the politics of peacekeeping operations will form the crux of this article. To make the context of the discussion intelligible and to justify the position of the argument, it is necessary to give more clarity or simplify the following concepts, *Peacekeeping* and *International Politics*.

¹ Peacekeeping / Peace Enforcement. Richard Caplan in Encyclopedia Princetoniensis: <https://pesd.princeton.edu/node/561>.

² Historical Timeline of UN Peacekeeping: <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/historical-timeline-of-un-peacekeeping>.

³ PEACEKEEPING.UN.ORG/PRINCIPLES-OF-PEACEKEEPING

⁴ 75 Years of United Nations Peacekeeping: Peace Begins With Me. <https://www.un.org/en/exhibits/exhibit/75-years-un-peacekeeping>

⁵ Our History: United Nations Peacekeeping. <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/our-history>

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Understanding Peacekeeping: www.accord.org.za/conflict-trends/understanding-peacekeeping

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION:

The two key concepts that will be used recurrently in this article are *peacekeeping* and *international politics*. However, clarification is necessary to understand the work's trajectory.

PEACEKEEPING:

There is no universal definition for peacekeeping. Even the United Nations' charter does not provide any definition of what a peacekeeping operation is, therefore its characteristics have been created over time.⁸ The need to avert the potential escalation of local conflicts into superpower confrontations during the Cold War, coupled with an inability to act, led to the development of peacekeeping.⁹

The Princeton Encyclopedia of Self-determination defines peacekeeping as the deployment of national or, more commonly, multinational forces for the purpose of helping to control and resolve an actual or potential armed conflict between or within states.¹⁰

Biehl (1994) also defines peacekeeping from the traditional view as the imposing of interposition forces following cessation of armed hostility and with the permission of the state on whose territory those forces are deployed to discourage a renewal of military conflict and promote an environment under which the underlying dispute can be resolved.¹¹

The previous definitions have some clear connections even with their nuances. Both sources agree to the fact that a peacekeeping mission is intended to bring an end to conflict between or within states.

INTERNATIONAL POLITICS:

A lot of definitions of international politics exist in the extant literature. Unfortunately, we cannot consider all. However, a few will be examined based on their relevance to article.

⁸ Expanding UN Peacekeeping Operations Since 1990: www.e-ir.info/2013/01/18/expanding-un-peacekeeping-operations-since-1990/

⁹ Richard Kareem Al-Qaq, 'Managing World Order: United Nations Peace Operations and the Security Agenda', in Expanding UN Peacekeeping Operations Since 1990: www.e-ir.info/2013/01/18/expanding-un-peacekeeping-operations-since-1990/

¹⁰ Encyclopedia Princetoniensis The Princeton Encyclopedia of Self-Determination: [Http://pesd.princeton.edu/?q=node/259](http://pesd.princeton.edu/?q=node/259)

¹¹ 'Biehl quoted in Lecture Note

In his influential work, "Theory of International Politics", Kenneth Waltz maintains that "International politics is the realm of the recurrence of war and of repeating efforts to control it in one way or another. With many sovereign states, with no system of law and virtually no opportunity for organizational entities to arrive at a stable formulation of their interests, conflict, sometimes leading to war, is bound to occur."¹² In "Politics Among Nations", Hans J. Morgenthau asserts that "International politics, like all politics, is a struggle for power. Whatever the ultimate aims of international politics, power is always the immediate aim."¹³

The above definitions and observations of international politics hint that the dynamic interaction of states in the international political system affects the nature of peacekeeping operations. Hardly surprising that some peacekeeping mandates are broad while others are narrow and well-defined.¹⁴ Put differently, the variation in mandate flexibility is a reflection of the inherent need for conflict resolution and interest projection.¹⁵

PEACEKEEPING IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL POLITICS

*The fullest perspective of peacekeeping
Is one which places it firmly in the
Context of international politics.- Alan James*

The above is an excerpt from Alan James' book, Peacekeeping in International Politics. The extract succinctly describes how peacekeeping operations are shaped by the dynamics of international politics. International politics is not linear, it is full of intrigues. A lot of twists occur as states interact with one another in the international system. Sometimes, these twists rub off on peacekeeping as actors define mandates, uphold them, and execute missions. The

¹² Kenneth N. Waltz, Theory of International Politics:
https://dl1.cuni.cz/pluginfile.php/486328/mod_resource/content/0/Kenneth%20N.%20Waltz%20Theory%20of%20International%20Politics%20Addison-Wesley%20series%20in%20political%20science%20%20%20%201979.pdf

¹³ Hans J. Morgenthau, Politics Among Nations: The Struggle for Power and Peace.
[http://slantchev.ucsd.edu/courses/ps240/04%20Conflict%20with%20States%20as%20Unitary%20Actors/Morgenthau%20-%20Politics%20among%20nations%20\(selected%20chapters\).pdf](http://slantchev.ucsd.edu/courses/ps240/04%20Conflict%20with%20States%20as%20Unitary%20Actors/Morgenthau%20-%20Politics%20among%20nations%20(selected%20chapters).pdf)

¹⁴ The Politics of Peacekeeping: UN Security Council Oversight Across Peacekeeping Missions I:
<https://academic.oup.com/isq/articles-abstract/58/3/621/1797809>

¹⁵ Ibid

United Nations Security Council is a battleground where the big powers assert themselves on every matter including those that are connected to peacekeeping.

One of the UN's primary responsibilities is the promotion of global peace. Peacekeeping is a vital instrument the UN seeks to achieve this. The UN Peacekeepers are usually deployed to conflict zones by the Security Council in line with the consent of the host states to maintain a ceasefire or de-escalate conflict depending on their mandate. While on their assignment, the UN Peacekeepers are obliged to be neutral, use minimal force, and act within the mandate of their operation. However, the dynamics of international politics usually challenge these traditional principles. This is evident in the behavior of the big powers who are also occupying a permanent seat in the UN Security Council.

Each of the big powers usually tries to influence the mandate of peacekeeping operations to reflect their interests. This was a common occurrence during the Cold War. The Cold War was a period when the world was bi-polarized. In other words, the world was divided into two ideological blocs -the East and the West or Communism vs Capitalism. The United States and its allies represented the West while the Soviet Union and its allies represented the East. However, the United States and the Soviet Union were the two superpowers. The bipolar nature of the international system contributed to a situation whereby the superpowers used peacekeeping as a tool to pursue their political agendas. For instance, the UN resolutions 143, 146, and 161 in the Congo crisis¹⁶ during the Cold War lends credence to the claim.

The post-Cold War era also witnessed how the political interests of the big powers played out when the UN attempted to deploy its peacekeeping force. For example, the UN was unable to deploy sufficient peacekeepers to Rwanda¹⁷ to stop the genocide that wiped out more than 800,000 Tutsi. This happened because the US and UK vetoed the decision of the Security Council to deploy troops.¹⁸ Again, when a Canadian peacekeeping commander in Rwanda, General Romeo Dallaire informed the UN about imminent attacks, the office of the Secretary-General dismissed him.¹⁹ After the killings, the international community realized that the great powers had interest, and they also had "UN-interest".²⁰ The refusal of the UN Security Council to deploy sufficient peacekeepers to halt the Rwanda genocide reveals the extent to which the big powers' interests can influence peacekeeping or reduce it to politics.

Peacekeeping mandates are temporary. Its multi-dimensional approaches usually manifest according to the whims and caprices of international politics. Some missions are broad in scope (Transition Peacekeeping, wider peacekeeping, and peace enforcement fall into this category) while some are narrow. It must be mentioned that peacekeeping has deviated from the traditional approach to multi-dimensional approaches. Not only because of the

¹⁶ Power to Veto: The UN and the Politics of Superpowers: www.nation.co.ke/lifestyle/DNZ/powers/957860-2004248-4kabu92/index.html

¹⁷ Ibid

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Ibid

dynamics of new wars but also because of the underlying interests of the big powers. The peace enforcement mandate is now being used as a pretext to side with one party against another. While this violates the principle of impartiality it can also be viewed as a subtle way the big powers project their interests. Jeni in quoting the UN Security Council Resolution 2098(2013) succinctly puts it:

In a number of its recent decisions, the UN Security Council has asked peacekeepers essentially to take sides in conflict affected societies, including by authorizing an intervention brigade to conduct offensive operations in order to neutralize rebel forces in the eastern Democratic Republic of Congo.²¹

Partiality is a clear violation of the principle of impartiality and a big digression from the classical approach of peacekeeping. The UN Peacekeepers are at risk of losing credibility if the big powers continue to use it as a political instrument to further their interests.

CONCLUSION:

The deployment of peacekeeping missions is subject to the approval of the Security Council. The big powers who are usually driven by interest constitute the Security Council as permanent members. While the big powers attempt to project their interests, they significantly shape the nature, scope, and mandate of peacekeeping. This is the unfortunate condition of UN peacekeeping between the time of its establishment and the post-Cold War world. No matter the mandate of a peacekeeping operation, it will always have an element of international politics because of the interests of the big powers. The United States especially, likes to be the police of the world. Therefore, it will use its big influence in the Security Council to achieve its political objectives even if it has to disguise as a peacekeeping force.

²¹ ‘UN Security Council Resolution 2098(2013)’, in Jeni Whalan Partial Peace: The Politics of Taking Sides in UN Peacekeeping, Paper prepared for International Studies Association Annual Convention, Toronto, 26-29 March 2014

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Lecture Notes:

1. Biehl quoted in lecture note.